

Imprinting system alterations in humans with multiple sclerosis.

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We integrated findings from measurement of total transcription across multiple tissue settings in humans with multiple sclerosis, in the brain and in the blood, to understand dysregulation of gene expression in demyelinating autoimmune disease. We demonstrate here alterations in the imprinting system in humans with multiple sclerosis. Homeobox factors proximal to Xist in the imprinting system functioning in normal epigenetic imprinting-based gene regulation in somatic cells, homeobox factors of the Dlx and Olig family, were activated in the brain and in the whole blood: this included *Dlx4* and *Dlx5*. A central component of the recently defined Xist RNP complex, the interleukin enhancer factor *Ilf3*, was significantly reduced in expression in the CNS in humans with MS. These data describe for the first time alterations in the imprinting system in humans with multiple sclerosis.

Citations

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